
The Use of Election Campaign Banners to Develop Communication Skills

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Abstract

Developing communication skills among students is an interesting and difficult task for the teacher. The teachers keep himself/herself busy thinking about innovative and interesting activities every time so that the student should take an interest in the activities and the teacher should meet the expected goal. If the students get surprised by the activity organized by the teacher for communication skills, they get enthusiastic about participating in the activities. Therefore, if the teacher uses different activities for developing communication skills, students become a good communicator. Even the teacher also takes an interest in exciting that activity. In this research paper, the researcher tries to find out the effectiveness of a new tool, which is the Election Campaign Banner, and for it, he designed many interesting activities to enhance communication skills.

Keywords: Election Campaign Banner, Communication skills, posters, etc.

Introduction:

After Globalization, the whole World converted into a village, and as a result of this, the aspirants got the opportunity to set up and spread their businesses according to their interests wherever they were comfortable. Not only recognized or popular companies have been expanding their business in other countries, but also new companies have been coming up with their business. As the business grows, the requirement for assets grows. Manpower is the main asset of any organization. Therefore, there is a huge demand from these companies for skilled manpower. Just having domain knowledge is not sufficient. Communication skills became one of the most important skills, along with domain knowledge. Engineering institutions and, ultimately, teachers play an important role in enhancing their skills. To develop communication skills among the students, the teachers have to think about innovative and interesting activities every time. If the students get surprised by the activity for their communication skills, they are enthusiastic about participating in the activities. Therefore, if the teacher uses different activities for developing communication skills, students become a good communicator. Even the teacher also takes an interest in exciting that activity. In this research paper, the researcher has used Election Campaign Banner for the activities to enhance communication skills.

Rational of the Study:

There are two concepts; Language acquisition and Language learning. Language acquisition is based on the neuro-psychological processes (Maslo, 2007: 41). It is a subconscious process by which children acquire their first language, which is their mother tongue (Kramina, 2000: 27). Language learning is a conscious process. It is the product of either a formal learning situation or a self-study program (Kramina, 2000: 27). When a second language is introduced to the learner, he/she undergoes the process of language learning. Here learner learns all the aspects of the language consciously. For developing communication skills, students require learning and then slowly moving towards second language acquisition. There are many activities that motivate learners to learn communication skills. The researcher found that students are more interested in election campaign banners and decided to use them for the present experiment.

Literature Review:

"Cartoon is an excellent form of expression, which can deliver positive messages and can create awareness among learners as the characters speak to you and narrate the whole story through their gestures," says Ian Diamond, the senior vice president, and General Manager of Turner Entertainment Networks Asia, Inc (TENA) (Dr. A.G. Sudha, Factors Influencing The Change In Behaviour Of Children On Viewing Cartoon Programs, 2004).

As cited in Bracher (1998), Handron (1994) states that poster presentations provide a platform for students to explore facts and understand concepts, thus arousing their curiosity and boosting their motivation and enthusiasm. Basically, notes Carter (2013), a "poster is a visual aid that should attract members of the audience and further support spoken communication between the author and the audience."

Method:

The researcher used the Election Campaign Banners to develop communication skills. The activities have been designed in such a way that the learners would get to expose in listening, reading, writing, and speaking. In every class, the learners were assigned different activities. The opportunities were provided to every learner. The survey method was used for collecting information on whether learners benefited from the experimented activities.

Discussion:

The researcher used the students of Computer Science & Engineering and Electrical & Electronics Engineering of the first semester of Gaya College of Engineering, Gaya Bihar, as sample students for the experiment. Activities like role play, presentation, group discussion, interview, writing an application, writing questionnaire for the interview, writing script, reading application, listening speeches, listening opinions, etc., have been designed and conducted. Following are the activities.

Speaking Skills:

1. Supposing that you are on testing an election for ward councillor, address the audience.
2. Assuming that you are contesting an election first time, address the audience by pointing out the failures of the sitting candidate.
3. Considering that you were the sitting ward councillor and now contesting an election, address the

audience.

4. Imagine that you are contesting an election for ward councillor. The Election Commission assigned you a particular symbol (ex., Deer, TV, Rising Sun, Flower, Hammer, Kite, etc.); address the audience by using the symbol as a tool of motivation.
5. Predicting that you are contesting an election for Ward Councillor, address the volunteers.
6. Think that you are contesting an election for Ward Councillor; address the group of people to vote for you.
7. Considering that you are the friend of contesting candidate (Ward Councillor), address the group of people to vote for him.
8. Assuming that you are contesting an election for ward councillor, discuss in the group to prepare the strategies to win.
9. Assuming that the election for councillor has been announced. You and your friend are voters. Interact with him/her on Mobile.
10. Assuming that you are the manager of drama. A candidate hired you for the campaign and asked you to perform a street play.
11. Assuming that you are contesting the election for Ward Councillor, you came to your home and sat with other family members and discussed the condition.
12. Imagine that you are contesting an election for Ward Councillor. Listen to the points raised by other candidates against you and address the audience.
13. Considering that your friend wants to contest an election. Meet the Advocate for legal advice and documentation.
14. Predicting that you want to contest an election. Meet the Election Commissioner and submit an application.
15. Consider that you are a citizen of a ward where the posters of the election campaign have been hung. An old illiterate lady sees those banners and asks for your help to understand them.

16. Suppose that your friend is contesting an election; he asked you to book the auto for the campaign. Meet the auto owner and fix it.
17. Imagine that your friend is contesting an election; he asked you to print the material for the campaign. Meet the printing owner and deal.
18. Think that you are contesting an election for a ward councilor; during the campaign, you meet a group of people who is not interested in voting. Interact with them.
19. Imagine that you are contesting an election for a ward councilor; a disabled person is not interested in voting. Meet with him/her and convince.
20. Suppose that you are contesting an election for a ward councilor; a group of people does not like you. Meet them and convince them.
21. Predicting that you are the Election Officer, aware of the new voters about their rights and appeal to them to participate in voting.
22. Envisage that you are contesting an election for a ward councilor; You are giving an interview to the reporter before the election day.
23. Envisage, imagine, predict, think of
24. During the writing skills activity, the instructor conducts the interactive session and asks some questions. Students get the chance to address the questions.

Writing Skills:

of a contesting election candidate. Prepare a detailed report with taking help of the survey.

4. Assume that a contesting election candidate is distributing the gifts and asking for the vote in your area. Write down a complaint letter to the Chief Election Officer.
5. Suppose that you are contesting an election and want to organize a rally. Write a letter to the Police station / Superintendent of Police.
6. Predicting that you are contesting an election. Write a letter to the municipal corporation for permission to hang the posters in the area.

1. Assume that you are contesting an election; design your campaigning banner.

2. Consider that you are contesting an election; prepare the speech to attract the voters.

3. Imagine that you are the voter. You want to add some problems of your area in the manifesto

7. Think that a contesting election candidate hires your team to perform the street play. Write the script for it.
8. Assume that you are contesting an election. Appeal to the best volunteers.
9. Consider that you want to contest an election. Find out the ten characteristics in you for the suitability of the post.
10. Suppose you are the supporter of a contesting election candidate. Write a Facebook blog to campaign for him.
11. Predicting that you are contesting an election. Write the Twitter blog.
12. Think that you are the contesting election candidate. You have been criticized by your opponents. Prepare your speech.
13. Consider that you are the news editor. Write news about the rally organized by a contesting election candidate for the English newspaper.
14. Assume that you are a contesting election candidate and want to send emails to the voters requesting a vote for you. Draft an email.
15. The instructor shared the pieces of papers written by the students in previous practicals and asked them to edit them.

Listening Skills:

1. The speech given by a leader (Mr. Nitish Kumar) during the election is played, and asked to note down the important points.
2. Students will listen to the Group Discussion (conducted in the language Lab) and note down the important points.
3. Students will be asked to see the Role plays (conducted for speaking skills) and give their feedback.
4. Students will be asked to listen to the JantaDarbar of Hon'able Nitish Kumar, Chief Minister of Bihar, and note down the problems of the common people.
5. A group of five girl students has been asked to discuss the issues faced by the women in their area. Other students have been asked to note the points.
6. A group of six boys' and girls' students has been asked to discuss the issues people are facing in their area. Other students have been asked to note the points.
7. Students have been asked to watch the recorded videos of the role plays performed by the student at the speaking skills activity and prepare their feedback.

Reading Skills: The instructor distributes the collected responses underwriting skills among the different groups of the same class and asks them to give their response. (One practical session will be used for this activity).

1. As a competent authority, read the letter received in the municipal corporation office submitted by a contesting election candidate and provide a suitable reply.

2. As a competent authority, Read the letter received in the Police station submitted by a contesting election candidate and prepare the response.
3. Read the material from the banner and make the correction if necessary.
4. Read the instructions given by the candidate to the volunteers, and if necessary, do the corrections.
5. Read the script of the street play and make the necessary changes, if required.
6. Read the reports of the previous election and prepare your strategy to win the election.
7. Read the pamphlets and other campaigning materials of the opposition candidates and prepare your counter.
8. Read the news published in the newspaper of your area regarding the election or election campaign. And write down important points for your campaign.
9. Search how to write emails for sending to the voters.

Findings:

In the end, a Google form was circulated among the students of Sem I who opted for Electrical and Electronics Engineering and Computer Science & Engineering at Gaya College of Engineering, Gaya. In the feedback form, the researcher asked the information about student satisfaction under five heads – Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and strongly Disagree. Out of 120, 74 students submitted their responses. They provided their feedback according to their experience.

The researcher got very surprising data. 87.8% of students actually participated in the activities in which the Election Campaign Banners were used to develop communication skills, and 12.2% of students did not participate, but they submitted their feedback. 93.2% of students said that the activities which developed reading, writing, speaking, and listening were conducted by using Election Campaign Banners. Addressing the information that the activities designed by the teacher by using Election Campaign Banner have helped the students to improve their communication skills, 54.1% opted for

Strongly Agree and 41.9% are with Agree, and 4.00% of students are with the side of Neutral. It may be said that 100% of participants admit that Election Campaign Banner helped to improve their communication, Skills. Addressing the question, Election Campaign Banner motivated the students to involve in communication skills activities; 54.1% of respondents chose the Strongly Agreed option, 40.5% of respondents were with the

Agreed side, and 5.4% of respondents were Neutral. It can be said that 100% of respondents agreed with the point that Election Campaign Banner motivated the participants to involve in communication skills activities. Reply to the question that "Election Campaign Banners should be used to develop communication skills?" 97.3% of students gave a positive reply, but 1.3% of students said Neutral, and 1.4% of students replied disagree.

Sr. No.	Question	Response
1	Name of the College	<p>● Gaya College Of Engineering, Gaya</p> <p>100%</p>
2	Name of the Branches	<p>● Electrical and Electronics Engineering ● Computer Science & Engineering</p> <p>51.4% 48.6%</p>
3	Have you participated in the activities in which the Election Campaign Banners were used to develop communication Skills?	<p>● Yes ● No</p> <p>87.8% 12.2%</p>
4	Have reading, writing, speaking, and listening activities been conducted by using Election Campaign Banners?	<p>● Yes ● No</p> <p>93.2% 6.8%</p>

5	Do you think the activities designed by the teacher by using Election Campaign Banner have helped you to improve your communication skills?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly Agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly Disagree
6	Do you think Election Campaign Banner motivated the students to involve in the communication skills activities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly Agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly Disagree
7	Do you think Election Campaign Banners should be used to develop communication skills?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly Agree ● Agree ● Neutral ● Disagree ● Strongly Disagree

Conclusion:

On the whole, it is said that the Election Campaign Banner is one of the best tools the English teacher may use to develop the communication skills of the students. The teacher can design activities that motivate the learner to improve their listening skills, speaking skills, reading skills, and writing skills. The students will also enjoy these activities because they get the actual experience of speaking like a leader, writing like a leader, giving permission like an officer questioning like an authoritative person. It is because they witness such activities somewhere in society, and therefore the students take much interest in the activities and involve themselves from their heart. They enjoyed it a lot, and finally, their communication gets improved.

Limitation and Scope of the Research:

The present research has been carried out at Gaya College of Engineering, Gaya, Bihar with the students of two branches of engineering, namely Computer Science & Engineering and Electrical & Electronics Engineering of Semester I. All students of the college have not been included. Further study may include students from various colleges of all the branches from I to IV years' students.

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